

“Changing World Order and India”

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Abstract:

The global system has seen transformations since First World War, again after Second World War, cold war and post-cold war. In all changes many unpredictable changes were brought in global politics such as after First and Second World Wars, Europe ceased to be the centre of power. USA and Russia got engaged in cold war that led to disintegration of Russian federation by the end and USA's triumphant victory as a sole superpower. Again rise of china at the global stage and emergence of regional powers dominated the field of global politics. The present paper sought to examine the changing global order and the role of India.

Key Words: International Relations, International Terrorism, Cold War, Multi-Polar, Bi-Polar, Uni-Polar, NAM Policy, Weapons of Mass destruction, NPT, Liberalization, Privatization, Globalization, Pokhran-II,

Introduction:

The course of international relations is subject to changes in the environment and has undergone drastic changes since the beginning of World War I (1914), World War II (1939), and the Cold War, which began in 1943-45 and lasted until 1991. In the post-Cold War period, the United States was the only superpower that dominated international politics for a long time, but certain events again brought about changes in international politics. The most important of these were the attack on the WTC on September 11, 2001, the emergence of international terrorism, the issue of nuclear proliferation, global warming, and the emergence of a multipolar world system. The event of September 11, 2001, decisively altered relations between states and superpowers, and scholars have constantly grappled with the precise nature of today's international system. While some believe that current international relations are in transition, others argue that international relations today are in disarray, a group of experts argue that the current international system is moving toward a multipolar world and losing its identity as a unipolar world under American leadership. During World War I and World War II, the world witnessed the existence of a multipolar power system. The end of World War II cleared the way for a bipolar power system, commonly known as the Cold War era, in which the U.S. and USSR remained the two superpowers in the world, in conflict with each other on the ideological front. From 1945 onward, the world divided into two power blocs, capitalist and communist, and in between, non-alignment emerged as a third front that took a neutral stance on power politics.

After the end of the Cold War, a unipolar system emerged under the leadership of the USA and the sad demise of the Soviet Union (USSR). Since 1991, the U.S. has continued to influence international politics, which is now

changing due to the emergence of regional powers created by the liberalization of their economies (e.g., India), some countries considered regional hegemony (e.g., China), and some other countries that have great influence despite their small size (e.g., North Korea and Iran)¹. At the same time, the U.S. is losing its significance as the only superpower in the world due to its crippled economy and heavy debt burden caused by George W. Although the U.S. still retains its defense capabilities and is superior to others, its economy has collapsed and it wanted to restore it by all means, while the means for the U.S. problems are in South Asia, where India has been identified as a potential power and economic target, at the same time China has awakened and jumped into the Asian market, in terms of arms supply China is the leading nation, as mentioned in the Pentagon's annual report that between 2007 and 2011 China sold nearly 811 billion conventional weapons to several countries around the world. In South Asia, the U.S. faces China as an economic and strategic threat. On the other hand, North Korea and Iran have emerged as illicit nuclear powers and have flaunted their nuclear capabilities, which is perceived by America as a security threat, and India is also seen as an emerging regional power in Asia. While it does not have defense capabilities comparable to China's, it undoubtedly has the ability to deter China and Pakistan and ensure peace and stability in the region. It was only after the end of the Cold War that India gained strategic and economic importance in international politics as it entered the process of globalization and economic liberalization.

During the Cold War, India remained inactive in world politics with its policy NAM and refused to join either of the two power blocs, as socio-economic development was India's top priority after independence, although the U.S. had recognized India's strategic importance before independence: in 1942, U.S. President Roosevelt

supported the Indian independence movement and won much goodwill from the Indian people by sympathizing with the freedom movement, but India's refusal to join the war front and Subhas Chandra Bose's support of the Axis powers were a fatal blow to Indo-American relations. After independence, India explored policies NAM, which were seriously challenged because of its friendship with the Soviet Union, eventually culminating in the 1971 "Indo-Soviet Friendship Treaty." India's pro-Soviet stance forced the U.S. to strengthen its relations with Pakistan and later China, which were traditional enemies of India and strategically isolated India, this development led India to choose the nuclear option in the time of Indira Gandhi, which further worsened India's position, because like India's confusing policy NAM, India's nuclear program was also seen as confusing and ambiguous, as India's nuclear test in 1974 was called a "Peaceful Nuclear Explosion"(PNE), but in describing details V.C. Trivedi, the representative to the Eighteen Nations Disarmament Committee, stated, "All nuclear tests are basically evil; they promote evil, and the sooner the evil is eliminated, the better." This shows that there is little difference between military and peaceful nuclear testing, since India was on the Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty's hit list until Bush took office as U.S. president. India's foreign policy was treated as "vogue" in the sense that it could not define what exactly was meant by NAM because it had entered into a strategic alliance with the Soviet Union. The drastic change in India's status in the world order came with India's adoption of liberalization, privatization, and globalization (LPG model) and recognized the fact that India cannot remain isolated from the globalization process for long. The liberalization process initiated during the Rajiv Gandhi era, which brought unprecedented economic growth and development, resulted in the U.S. facing economic recession, higher unemployment rate, and extreme debt burden during the Bill Clinton era. India-U.S. trade relations improved and a strong foundation was laid for an India-U.S. economic and strategic partnership, but the issue of the Nuclear Non-proliferation Treaty remained a vexation in their relations.

In 1998, relations deteriorated further when India conducted a series of nuclear tests popularly known as 'Pokaran II' during the tenure of Atal Bihari Vajpayee, and India was subsequently declared a nuclear state, but India continued to be viewed as the most favourable economic destination. The further transformation The further transformation in India's status came with the arrival of Gorge Bush as a president of America in 2001 who has to change the complete picture of South Asia after assuming the office, the first major task before him was to frame his foreign policy in

which India has to play more comprehensive role as a strategic partner certain factors can be attributed to such changes, the first important factor was the attack on WTC on 9/11 by terrorist which generated a kind of sympathy in US about India's victimization at the hands of Pakistan sponsored terrorism, followed by Bush admiration of Indian democracy whereas the third factor was rise of China. The Indo-US relations culminated in Next Step in Strategic Partnership (NSSP) which resulted in the Indo-US civilian nuclear cooperation agreement, giving India a tacit recognition as a 'De Facto' Nuclear state status. In the last two decades, India continued to enjoy close strategic relations with USA.

India's importance acquired attention in the eyes of US policy makers against the changing Geo-strategic landscape of South Asia and emergence of china as an aggressive nation which has resorted rapid military modernization and aggressive marketing policies have anticipated as an agent of danger for regional peace & security, china's relations with problem countries like Pakistan as a counterweight to India, likewise its relations with countries like Iran, Sudan, Venezuela and its special economic policy towards Middle east, Africa, Latin America is perceived as threat to US security. The developments in South Asia are not healthy for regional peace in particular & world order in general. The present world order is in transition and marching towards multi-polar system but it should be noted that all powers are not identical and have certain conflictual relations while some of them are using nuclear leverage for bargaining others focuses on its economic and military modernization and warfare capabilities as to change the existing single power domination in between them India is emerging as very crucial regional player with its legacy of peaceful co-existence and promoting peace & stability in the world. Since long time India has shown tolerance towards China & Pakistan regarding boundary disputes, it has developed nuclear weapons which are basically political weapons in nature and used for purely deterrence purpose in this context it has laid down the principle of 'No First Use' and encourages elimination of nuclear weapons from the world. Indo-US nuclear deal is concluded on the assumption that though not signed NPT, India has never violated nuclear laws and Non-proliferation treaty. India is active in the regional economic integration via SAARC, ASEAN and BRIC etc. India's approach towards international problems remains cooperative, optimistic and peaceful.

While describing present world order scholars professed the emergence of multi-polar world, in which some powers represents 'Theocratic states' some as communist powers and in between

them some are praising democratic values, other scholars argued that, once again world is moving back towards Bi-polar system led by USA and China and may pave way for Bi-polar rivalry, still other hold that any nation like china though projected high economic growth and military capabilities cannot compete with USA in the near future, whatever the arguments put by the scholars it is true that world is marching towards multi-polar system in which the role of India is very crucial in maintaining peace & stability in the world India is identified as the leader of developing nations it also propagates the necessity of nuclear disarmament, while doing so India never violated nuclear non-proliferation efforts, it always promote peaceful use of nuclear energy, which is evident in the statement of India's first prime minister Jawaharlal Nehru who expressed on 20th Jan. 1957 that "No man can prophecy the future, but should like to say on behalf on my govt. & I think, I can say with some assurance on behalf of any future govt. of India that whatever might happen, whatever the circumstances, we shall never use Atomic energy for evil purpose. There is no any condition attached to this assurance because one's condition is attached, the value of assurance does not go very far." The present world order exhibits, the hard reality of realist arguments as now, every small, big and middle powers have realized the utility of their power projection hence, the world today, has witnessed the truth of arms race, proliferation of Weapons of Mass Destruction (WMD), terrorism etc. likewise, it also brought instability and uncertainty in the world order. No doubt, world needs multipolar power structure but it should be aimed at restoring balance of power and not for the dominance purpose. Now America seems to be convinced that, India can be proved to be an effective balancer in the region and its core foreign policy principles could be applied to ensure Just world order, because India being the victim of aggression at the hands of Pakistan & china never complicated the situation, likewise it has fall victim of Pakistan sponsored terrorism though it believes in peaceful means of resolution of this issue and by mutually acceptable principles as India bears major responsibility of maintaining peace & stability in the region, as the Asian continent has predicted to be the source of Third world war and identified as most sensitive place in the world because of the presence of multiple nuclear states and their relative confluxional relations with each other that followed by America's interventionist policy. All these developments are suggestive of India as an effective device to maintain stability, peace and to prevent regional wars which might lead to world war.

Conclusion:

India's image in the post-cold war era has improved unprecedented; it has also shown tolerance towards international as well as regional disputes & issues. It has acquired the status as economic destination in the eyes of western world it is conspicuous in the statement of India's finance minister P. Chidambaram, as while stressing more on the bilateral trade, he held that in 2002, the FDI of America reached to 227 million which again grew by 5.2 billion in 2012, which put India in the fast investing nation category in USA. In the strategic terms, India has gained the status as a balancer against china, the growing strategic partnership between India & US is indicative of this. Though emerging regional power India believes in peaceful co-existence, non-aggression similarly emphasis cooperative environment in the world, this thinking resembles with Idealist school of thought. World had witnessed the devastating impact of hegemonic ambitions during First & Second World Wars and the present international system also reveals the possibility of third world war with its epic Centre in Asia. Taking in to consideration all these arguments India's crucial role cannot be overruled India's foreign policy happened to be irreverent and vague has now recognized as important to maintain peace & stability in the world. The world is marching towards multi-polar system which is essential to maintain balance of power and the core of it lies in the peaceful rise of states, which India has been advocated for long time. India's peaceful rise is viewed as a welcome development because of peace & stability, restoring balance of power, peaceful co-existence, spreading democratic values and to limit aggression hence it is not wrong to conclude that India's rise is healthy for just and peaceful world.

References:

1. These countries have acquired leverage in International Relations because they possess nuclear technology, hence increased their bargaining power in International Relations.
2. China's arms supply to Pakistan, US report, DainikLoksatta, 8th may 2013, pg.9
3. AsthanaVandana, India's foreign policy & subcontinental politics, Kanishka publishers, New Delhi, 1999, pg. 287
4. ChakamaBhumitra, Towards Pokhran –II-explaining India's Nuclearization process, Cambridge Univ. press, 2005, pg. 214
5. Paddock Carl, India-US nuclear deal-prospects & implications, Epitome books, New Delhi, 2009, pg. 137.
6. Ghai U.R, Foreign policy of India, New Academic publishing, Punjab, 2002, pg. 596
7. DainikLoksatta, Tuesday, 15th Oct. 2013, National & International news, pg. 9